

Mini-review

Group housing of calves

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CARE4DAIRY

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1. The issue

Under natural conditions, cows leave the herd shortly before parturition to calve in a secure place; this facilitates the dam-calf bond (Rørvang et al., 2018). For the first days of life the calf is entirely dependent on its mother's milk, with 8–12 suckling bouts/day (e.g. Cantor et al., 2019; Day et al., 1987). The mother-calf pair then reintegrate into the group (Bouissou, 2001). From two weeks of age, interactions with calves of the same age increase, these include social licking, allo-grooming and play (Bouissou, 2001; Whalin et al., 2021), and “crèche” (i.e. small groups of calves lying close to each other) may be formed (Sato et al., 1987). Distance from the mother gradually increases whilst the social relationship with other herd mates (adult and young) increases, though the maternal bond is maintained into adulthood (Bouissou, 2001; Sato et al., 1987). Studies conducted on group-housed calves showed that when grouped at birth or the within the first three days, calves establish strong and long-lasting bonds with each other (Bøe & Færevik, 2003; Duvé & Jensen, 2012). In natural environments, the calves have the opportunity to perform multiple social interactions with a wide range of partners of different ages and gender.

On commercial dairy farms, calves are separated from their dam either immediately or within a few hours or days after birth (De Passillé et al., 2008). Following separation, they are often kept alone. This applies to 60% of the dairy farms in Europe (Vasseur et al., 2010), 63% in the USA (USDA, 2016), 88% in Quebec (Vasseur et al., 2010) and 70% in Brazil (Hötzel et al., 2014). Amongst justifications for early separation from the dam are 1- the immaturity of the calves' immune system (Cortese 2009) that increases the risks of contamination through the mother (Faubert & Litvinsky, 2000; Muskens et al., 2003), 2- the development of the dam-calf bond that will then have to be broken (Flower & Weary, 2003), and 3- economic considerations (increase of saleable milk, Beaver et al., 2019). Subsequent social isolation is meant to protect young calves from disease (e.g. diarrhoea: Cho & Yoon, 2014 and Bovine Respiratory Disease (**BRD**): Griffin et al., 2010) and from performing undesirable behaviours such as cross-sucking (Lidfors & Isberg, 2003) or competition for food and aggression (von Keyserlingk et al., 2004). In contrast, some farmers choose to group-house dairy calves to reduce labour and save time (Hötzel et al., 2014).

The negative effects of early maternal deprivation and social isolation on calves' behaviour and welfare are well documented, with consequences such as increased reactivity (Veissier et al., 1997) and social (Lv et al., 2021; Santo et al., 2020) or cognitive (Gaillard et al., 2014; Meagher et al., 2015, 2017) deficits. In Europe, group housing is now mandatory for all calves from 8 weeks of age (Council Directive 2008/119/EC), but concerns remain for younger calves. This review focuses on the impacts of group housing on young calves' health, behaviour, welfare and performance as well as on the prerequisites for successful group housing. Cow-Calf contacts are addressed in a separate CARE4DAIRY review.

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

2.1. Group housing

During the first 8 weeks of life, dairy calves are motivated to seek social contact and spend about 2 % of their time engaged in social contact (Chua et al., 2002). They are willing to work for social contact with a familiar calf, and they work harder for full contact rather than contact restricted through bars (Holm et al., 2002).

2.2. Calf health

Enteric and respiratory diseases can be transmitted between calves via faecal-oral and nose-nose contacts and individual housing of calves is supposed to limit this transmission (Maatje et al., 1993; McGuirk, 2008; Steenkamer, 1982). However, scientific results are controversial: some studies report an increased risk of disease in group housed calves (Bertoni et al., 2021; Gulliksen et al., 2009), whilst others report no differences (Johnson et al., 2011; Mahendran et al., 2021) or even improved health in group housed calves (Babu et al., 2009; Hanekamp et al., 1994; Hänninen et al., 2003). Adequate milk feeding, hygiene (e.g. hygiene of bedding), ventilation, colostrum practices, and diet are crucial to minimise calf disease (Costa et al., 2016), and these factors probably outweigh the potential negative impact of group housing on calf health.

The size of the group seems to be important, with potentially higher transmission risks in larger groups (Losinger & Heinrichs, 1997; Svensson et al., 2003) or at least different propagation dynamics of the pathogens. This leads to increased risk of respiratory disease during the 1st month but decreased risks at 4 months (Abdelfattah et al., 2013). Pair housing is considered to be a viable alternative as it provides the opportunity for social contact whilst limiting the risk of disease transmission (less diarrhoea: Lindner et al., 2021) and improving calf immunity (Lv et al., 2021). Indeed, group housed calves have a more effective immune system than individually housed ones (Cobb et al., 2014).

On the contrary, repeatedly adding and removing calves to the group results in higher disease prevalence compared to maintenance of stable groups (Pedersen et al., 2009). In addition, having stable groups allows more effective cleaning of pens between consecutive groups, which ensures better hygiene.

2.3. Production

A review of 17 scientific publications revealed that all of the studies reported at least, equal performance of group housed calves in dry matter intake (**DMI**) of solid feed (concentrate or grass), average daily weight gain (**ADG**) and body weight when compared against individually housed calves (Costa et al., 2016). Of these 17 publications, 13

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

reported positive impacts of group housing on at least one of these performance indicators, irrespective of the size of the group (from 2 to 6 calves) and more importantly, none reported any negative effects.

2.3.1. Feed intake

Early studies, conducted in 1970–80' showed increased solid feed intake in pre-weaned calves raised with older animals (Warnick et al., 1977), probably due to social facilitation. More recent studies confirmed the increased feed intake in calves living with same age conspecifics (pair or group housed, Cobb et al., 2014; Costa et al., 2015; De Paula Vieira et al., 2010; Jensen et al., 2015; Meagher et al., 2015). During weaning, the results are mitigated, with studies reporting no effect of group housing on feed intake irrespective of the age of grouping (Bolt et al 2017) and others reported higher feed intake in group housed calves (Liu et al., 2020). After weaning, previously grouped (or paired) calves consume more solid feeds (Bernal-Rigoli et al., 2012; Cobb et al., 2014; De Paula Vieira et al., 2010; Duve et al., 2012; Lv et al., 2021; Mahendran et al., 2021; Overvest et al., 2018; Whalin et al., 2018) and visit the trough more often (De Paula Vieira et al., 2010).

2.3.2. Growth

The impact of group housing on calf growth is in the main positive. Before and after weaning, group housed calves grow faster (Cobb et al., 2014; Knauer et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Pempek et al., 2016; Valníčková et al., 2015) and have an equal (Wormsbecher et al., 2017) or higher (Costa et al., 2015; Pempek et al., 2016; Valníčková et al., 2015) final body weight than individually housed calves. During weaning, performance of group housed calves is at least equal to (Bolt et al., 2017) or better than that of individually housed calves, in terms of growth rate (Liu et al., 2020), average daily weight gain (Bernal-Rigoli et al., 2012; Jensen et al., 2015) and final body weight (Knauer et al., 2021).

Stable group or pair housing in the first weeks of life may ease the transition from milk to solid feed (Overvest et al., 2018). It also has a positive effect on milk production for females in later life, which is attributed to better growth during this crucial early stage (Soberon et al., 2012). However, repeated changes to group composition results in reduced weight gain when compared to stable groups (Pedersen et al., 2009).

2.4. Behaviour, cognition and welfare

2.4.1. Emotional reactivity

Group housing during the first weeks of life seems to decrease the animals' emotional response to novel foodstuffs (increasing consumption of unfamiliar foodstuffs Costa et al., 2014; Whalin et al., 2018), novel environments: Bučková et al., 2021; De Paula Vieira et al., 2010; De Paula Vieira, et al., 2012b; Jensen & Larsen, 2014) or novel conspecifics (De Paula Vieira et al., 2012b). When restrained for blood sampling, pair housed calves struggle less than isolated calves (Duve et al., 2012). The effects of group housing on emotional reactivity may disappear when group composition is destabilised. Emotional

reactions to novelty (e.g. novel object test, presence of a dog) have been shown to be more exaggerated in unstable groups compared to stable ones (Boissy et al., 2001).

2.4.2. Social behaviour

Group housing in the first weeks of life will increase calves' social skills (Bøe & Færevik, 2003; Lv et al., 2021 for a review). Previous experience of social interactions results in reduced hesitance in interacting (sniff and touch) with an unfamiliar conspecific (Jensen & Larsen, 2014) and an increase in positive interactions such as allo-grooming and social play (Lv et al., 2021). After weaning and grouping with unfamiliar conspecifics of the same age, calves with previous social experience (pair or group housed) spent more time lying close to conspecifics (Lindner et al., 2021). In the first week after grouping, pair housed calves still have a preferred relationship with their previous pen-mate (Bolt et al., 2017), suggesting that calves are able to bond with each other from the first weeks of life. Bonds between calves may help alleviate the stress of weaning by offering social support (Costa et al., 2016). Group housed calves vocalise less when milk feeding is stopped at weaning (Bolt et al., 2017; De Paula Vieira et al., 2010).

2.4.3. Play behaviour

Group housed calves display less locomotor play than those individually housed (Jensen et al., 2015). Group-housed calves however have opportunities for social play (Valníčková et al., 2015). When social and locomotor play behaviours are combined the occurrence of play behaviour does not differ between group and individually housed calves or is actually increased in the group housed calves (Duve et al., 2012; Jensen et al., 2015).

When released out of their crate into a larger pen, individually housed calves are more active than group housed calves (Bučková et al., 2021; Lv et al., 2021; Valníčková et al., 2015). This effect is likely to be the result of reduced calf movement in the small space available in crates rather than social deprivation (Dellmeier et al., 1985).

2.4.4. Stereotypic and abnormal behaviours

Early group housing significantly decreases the prevalence of stereotypic and abnormal behaviours (e.g. non-nutritive sucking, tongue rolling) when compared to individual housing (Lv et al., 2021; Pempek et al., 2016). However, cross-sucking, considered as a problem because of the potential for disease transmission (e.g. infections), can be present in group housed calves, where it is prevented in individually housed calves (Lidfors & Isberg, 2003; Pempek et al., 2016). Cross-sucking in group housed calves is not however inevitable and many studies reported that it was not observed (Chua et al., 2002; Wormsbecher et al., 2017), suggesting that management practices, in particular providing milk through teats, can reduce this problem (Reipurth et al., 2020) (see below 3. How to group house calves successfully: Recommendations for group housing of calves).

2.4.5. Aggression-competition

In group housed calves, resource guarding behaviours may increase if access to feeders – teats or troughs – is restricted (e.g. only 1 teat for two or three calves, von Keyserlingk et al., 2004). Housing conditions have no impact on aggression when the design of the feeding area (barriers between teats: Jensen et al., 2008) or feed distribution (increased teats-to-calves ratio: von Keyserlingk et al., 2004; increased availability of milk: Jensen & Budde, 2006) are adapted to minimise resource guarding.

Social instability will result in an increase in aggressive interactions, even in previously socialised animals (Mounier et al., 2006). This instability usually occurs after weaning, when calves are grouped with unfamiliar conspecifics.

2.4.6. Cognitive abilities

Pair or group housed calves and calves raised with their dam perform better in a reverse learning task, when compared to individually housed calves (Gaillard et al., 2014; Meagher et al., 2015). After training to discriminate between two objects with only one object associated with a positive reinforcer, pair or group housed calves make less errors when the object associated to the positive reinforcer changes, when compared to individually housed calves.

2.5. Impact of age at grouping

There is no effect of age at grouping, when considering the occurrence of play behaviour (Reipurth et al., 2020). Early grouping was shown to increase solid feed intake (Costa et al., 2015) and to decrease emotional reactions at mixing (Chua et al., 2002; De Paula Vieira et al., 2012a; 2012b) and weaning (Bolt et al., 2017). In multi age groups, younger calves have more difficulty competing for access to milk (Jensen, 2007).

3. How to group house calves successfully: Recommendations for group housing of calves

3.1. Reducing cross-sucking

Cross-sucking is rare (or absent) in calves raised with their dams or foster cows (Jensen, 2003; Krohn et al., 1999; Margerison et al., 2003). Allowing the calves to access milk for several hours per day, through teats instead of buckets drastically reduces the occurrence of cross-sucking (Größbacher et al., 2018; Jensen & Budde, 2006; Lidfors & Isberg, 2003; Veissier et al., 2003) by providing the opportunity to perform closer to natural suckling behaviours (De Passillé et al., 2010; Salter et al., 2021).

Implementation of gradual weaning protocols reduces cross-sucking in calves (Nielsen et al., 2008) and supports transition from milk to solid feed (Keil & Langhans, 2001). Lack of water was identified as a factor increasing the risk of cross-sucking. Water should thus be provided ad libitum.

3.2. Reducing aggression/competition

Increasing the teat-to-calves ratio, providing several milk meals per day and increasing the quantity of milk provided (Jensen, 2004; von Keyserlingk et al., 2004) drastically reduces the prevalence of aggressive behaviours. Group stability before weaning decreases the prevalence of aggressive behaviours (Mounier et al., 2006). Following weaning, calf groups should come from no more than 2 previously stable groups to reduce aggression and favour positive social interactions (Færevik et al., 2007).

3.3. Health management

Particular attention has to be paid to the preparation of colostrum, milk and/or milk replacer in order to decrease the risk of contamination through feed ingestion (Sockett, 2020). Water should be of adequate quality (regarding mineral composition particularly). Feed must be handled with clean hands.

Favouring “all in/all out” systems with stable groups allows efficient and effective cleaning of pens between groups, thus reducing the risk of disease transmission (Pedersen et al 2009). Indoor housing should be protected from contamination from outdoors by enforcing use of footbaths and clean clothing protocols. Irrespective of the type of environment, feeding equipment should be carefully cleaned and sanitised, and the bedding provided should be thick (comfortable), clean, dry and dust free (Sockett, 2020).

In summary, group housing of calves can be performed successfully when

- Calves receive adequate amounts of good quality colostrum
- Calves are then fed adequate quantities of milk or milk replacer (see EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* mini-review ‘Frequency and quantity of milk feeding to dairy calves’)
- Milk (or milk replacer) is available for a large part of the day, e.g. several hours spread along daytime
- Milk (or milk replacer) is provided through teats, with one teat per calf
- The calf groups are kept stable
- Good hygiene practices are used in the maternity and calf pens
- Good hygiene practices are used for the preparation of milk and colostrum
- If mixing of calves is necessary, there should be no more than two groups mixed

4. Literature search

Search equations in WOS:

1. "Dairy calf" AND "group housing" in *topic*
→ **343 results**
2. "Dairy calf" AND "group housing" AND "management" in *topic*- 124 results, all in the 1st search
→ **0 additional results**
3. "Dairy calf" AND "group" AND "impact" in *topic* - 203 results. 37 in the 1st search
→ **166 additional results**
4. "Dairy calf" AND "housing" AND "impact" in *topic* - 82 results. 28 in the 1st or 3rd search
→ **54 additional results**
5. "Dairy calf" AND "social instability" in *topic* - 3 results, 1 in previous search
→ **2 additional results**
6. "Dairy calf" AND "group*" AND "management" in *topic* OR "Dairy calf" AND "group*" in *keywords* - 59 results. 34 results of equation 7 were included in previous search
→ **25 additional results**
7. "Dairy calf" AND "group*" AND "management" in *title* OR "Dairy calf" AND "group*" in *keywords* - 16 results
All the results of equation 7 are included in the results of the 6th search.
→ **0 additional results**

In total: 590 results amongst which 438 were excluded (see table below) → 152 references left

No. of publications excluded	Reason for exclusion
9	Not the right species (cattle)
115	Not target population (dairy calf)
314	Not group housing

From the remaining 152 publications, priority was given to review papers covering a wide range of subjects presented here and comparisons between individual and group housing.

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